

Titration of Hydrogen Clays with Pyridine and Quinoline

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Pyridine and quinoline have been found to give adsorption complexes with hydrogen clays. This character along with the basic nature and fair solubility in water of these heterocyclics suggested the possibility of their utilization as useful titrants for hydrogen clays. It has been found that the adsorption of these bases by clay minerals is equivalent to their base exchange capacity and they can be used for stoichiometric titrations of hydrogen clays. An improvement in the nature of curves and breaks is observed, both in conductometry and potentiometry when pyridine and quinoline are used as titrants. No multiple inflexions have, however been observed during the titrations of hydrogen montmorillonite, hydrogen illite and hydrogen kaolinite, with these bases. A correlation has been observed during the titration of binary mixtures of clay minerals with organic bases in that the cation exchange capacity (cec) values of the mixtures are in general agreement with the sum of cec of the individual clay minerals.

Investigations on the electrochemical nature of clays have long been an interesting field of study¹. Marshall, Mukherjee and their coworkers^{2, 3, 4, 5} have reported a number of papers on the electrometric titrations of clays. The neutralization curves of these polyacids were found to give inflexions which indicated weak acidic characteristics^{3, 6, 7}. With a view to obtaining more well defined and sharper inflexions at the end point of titrations, the method of titration in nonaqueous media was applied to these systems by Ganguly and coworkers⁸ as well as Singhal and Malik⁹. The inflexions obtained during the titrations of clay acids were explained on the concepts of crystallinity¹⁰ and the layer lattice structure¹¹ which postulated the existence of exchange spots with different bonding energies. According to Jackson¹², the aluminium ion bonds through oxygen formed a variety of functional groups which provided the cation exchange sites of layer lattice silicates. These played an important role in determining the nature of clay acidity.

Studies on clays also revealed that the clay possessed a strong preference for some organic cations which were often quantitatively adsorbed until all the exchange positions

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were occupied by the organic cation. Grim, Allaway and Cuthbert¹³ showed that small ions were adsorbed by clays only upto the cation exchange capacity, whereas larger ions were adsorbed in excess. Smith¹⁴, while studying the adsorption of alkaloids by clays from aqueous solutions noticed that the reaction between bentonite and salts of organic bases was principally one of base exchange, where saturation was indicated by flocculation. The weight of alkaloid adsorbed approached a definite limit and this limit represented equivalent quantities of the various alkaloids. The work of Spain and White¹⁵ revealed that organic bases, such as, tetraalkyl ammonium bases could be used as titrants for hydrogen aluminium bentonite. These observations coupled with the basic nature of pyridine, isoquinoline, as well as, their favourable solubility in water suggested the possibility of utilising these and similar other organic bases as useful titrants for clays. The present work with pyridine was undertaken with a view to examining the possibility of using it for the titration of clays and thereby characterising the latter on the basis of the features of the curves.

EXPERIMENTAL

The clay minerals used in these studies were obtained from Wards Natural So. establishment, New York. The mineral montmorillonite was from Amori, Mississippi, illite from Morris, Illinois, and kaolinite from Bath, South Caroline. The clays were isolated in the usual manner and converted into H-clays by passing the Na-clays through a column of H-Dowex-50W-X8 cation exchange resin as recommended by Aldrich and Buchanan¹⁶. The reagents viz., pyridine, quinoline and sodium hydroxide used were of pure grade.

10 cc of 1.5 to 2% of the clay suspensions were taken in pyrex glass tubes. To each of these samples varying amounts of the base (0.06*N* pyridine or 0.1*N* NaOH) were added and the suspension stirred occasionally for 3 hr. before recording *pH* and conductance. The stirring time and the total time for titrations were kept as uniform as possible. The readings were recorded with Beckman *pH* meter, Model G, with saturated calomel and glass electrode assembly. Conductivity measurements were carried out under exactly similar conditions with the help of Philips conductivity meter with dipping cell. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ maintained with the help of a thermostatic water bath. Binary mixtures of the clay minerals in 1 : 1 ratio by weight, obtained by mixing suspensions of known concentration, were also titrated in a similar manner. The cec values for the clays and their mixtures were evaluated from the inflexion points on the titration curves. The cec data were further verified by titration according to Ganguli's KCl-KOH method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Individual clay minerals and their binary mixtures on titration with pyridine and quinoline have yielded similar results both in conductometric as well as in potentiometric titrations on account of the close character of these two aromatic bases. For the sake of brevity results obtained with pyridine only are being reported here.

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To suitably characterise the clay samples, individual clay minerals and their binary mixtures were first titrated with sodium hydroxide. The results obtained are given in table I and the titration curves obtained are shown in figures 1 and 2. The shape of the curves and the nature of inflexions obtained agree with the work of Marshall and Krinbill and with the more recent work where hydrogen clays with minimal aluminium obtained after passing through columns of acidic exchange resins have been titrated with inorganic bases. No multiple inflexions have been noticed in either the titration of individual acid clays or their binary (1 : 1) mixtures with NaOH.

Having characterised the clay acids with NaOH, titrations were then undertaken with pyridine. With its noticeable basic properties, the interaction between pyridine and the hydrogen clays should yield a salt like addition product. During the addition of pyridine to the H-clays it is noticed that the conductance of the clay suspension decreases and the pH increases in a characteristic manner. This appears to be due to the loss of H⁺ ions as the pyridinium salt is formed which is possibly much less ionized than the H-clays. After all the H-clay has interacted the values for pH and conductance become more or less constant due to the nonpolar character of the pyridine molecule.

FIG. 1. CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION CURVES
FOR THE CLAYS AND THEIR MIXTURES WITH NaOH

The curves obtained during the conductometric and potentiometric titrations of the individual clay minerals and their binary mixtures with pyridine are shown in figures 3 and 4 and the results are presented in table I. A comparison of these curves with those obtained in the case of sodium hydroxide indicates that titrations with pyridine and quinoline give more well defined curves and the effect is much more marked in conductometry. Only

FIG. 2. pH TITRATION CURVES FOR THE CLAYS AND THEIR MIXTURES WITH NaOH

one inflexion is realised in the case of all the three type of clays, both in potentiometry as well as conductometry viz., at 60 me. in the case of montmorillonite, between 21.5 and 23 me. in the case of illite and at 5 me. in kaolinite. The breaks occur in the pH range 3.5 to 4.5 when the titrations are done with pyridine and in the pH range 6.5 to 7.5 when the NaOH is used as titrant. The cec values at which the breaks occur with NaOH and pyridine in case of the different clay minerals and their mixtures are nearly equal to each other and also in the neighbourhood of cec determined by KCl-KOH method (vide table I). This points to the fact that adsorption of pyridine by the clay minerals is almost in quantities equivalent to that of sodium. In the concentration range studied by us, stoichiometric titrations of hydrogen clays with pyridine are, therefore, possible, the end points of titrations indicating complete exchange, equivalent to the exchange capacity of the clay.

The titrations reveal that multiple inflexions, reported by some earlier workers^{4,5} are not realised in the case of illite and kaolinite when their freshly prepared ion exchanged pure H-clays containing negligible amounts of Al-clays are titrated with pyridine. This behaviour can find an explanation in the fact that during the interaction of pyridine with H-clays, only the negatively charged flat surface electrical diffuse layer is available for adsorption of pyridine. Being possibly positively charged at low pH values¹⁷, the diffuse double layer on the broken silica surface of the edges remains ineffective for subsequent adsorption. This results in one break only during the titrations. The monobasic nature of the acid clays can also be accounted for by the existence of acidic sites or spots on the

FIG. 3. CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION CURVES FOR THE CLAYS AND THEIR MIXTURES WITH PYRIDINE

flat layer surfaces of hydrogen clays which dominate over others in the interaction of H-clays with organic bases. This one kind of acid function only gives rise to a single break. The earlier conclusions on multiple inflexions were probably due to the effect of aluminium

FIG. 4. pH TITRATION CURVES FOR THE CLAYS AND THEIR MIXTURES WITH PYRIDINE

saturation in electro dialysed clays where the aluminohexahydronium monobasic cation¹², $Al(-OH_2, 0.5^+)_6$ itself acted as a weak acid giving rise to multiple inflexions.

TABLE I

Base exchange capacity values of the monomineralic clays and their mixtures as obtained with potentiometric titrations, conductometric titrations and the KCl-KOH method.

Mineral	Pyridine as titrant		Sodium hydroxide as titrant		Bec values in me/100gm clay by KCl-KOH method
	Bec values in me/100 gm clay with Potentiometry	Conductometry	Bec values in me/100 gm clay with Potentiometry	Conductometry	
	Only one inflexion is obtained at	Only one inflexion is obtained at	Only one inflexion is obtained at	Only one inflexion is obtained at	
Montmorillonite	60.0 (4.50) $pK = 2.80$	60.0	65.0 (6.70) $pK = 3.05$	65.0	63.0
Illite	21.5 (3.50) $pK = 2.65$	23.0	22.0 (6.80) $pK = 3.50$	18.0	34.4
Kaolinite	5.0 (4.15) $pK = 3.80$	5.0	5.0 (6.50) $pK = 4.35$	4.0	5.0
Montmorillonite Illite (1:1)	42.0 (3.80)	42.0	45.0 (6.90)	42.0	48.5
Montmorillonite Kaolinite (1:1)	32.0(4.25)	33.0	35.0 (6.90)	32.0	34.4
Illite Kaolinite (1:1)	11.0 (4.60)	12.0	12.0 (7.00)	11.0	20.3

(The pH values at the inflexion points of the clays are indicated in parentheses)

Considering the case of 1 : 1 binary mixtures of the clay minerals (figures 1 and 2, curves 4, 5 and 6) the results of conductometry and potentiometry show that the individual breaks for clay minerals merge into one break when the titrations are done with NaOH and interestingly enough the cec values obtained for the mixtures are additive of those of the individual minerals. Almost the same kind of interesting effect is observed when the titrations are done with pyridine (figures 3 and 4, curves 4,5 and 6). The masking effect and a reduction in the number of breaks realisable with mixtures is not surprising because of the narrow difference in the pK values (evaluated from the titration curves and shown in table I) of the different acids constituting the clay mixtures.

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